

Article

Phase Shift Effects in Chiral Plasmonic Nanohole Arrays

Franco Marabelli ^{1,*}
and Francesco Floris ^{1,*}

¹ Department of Physics, University of Pavia, Via Bassi 6, 27100 Pavia, Italy; giovanni.pellegrini@unipv.it (G.P.); luca.zagaglia@unipv.it (L.Z.)

² Paul Scherrer Institut, 5232 Villigen, Switzerland; konstantins.jefimovs@psi.ch (K.J.); dimitrios.kazazis@psi.ch (D.K.)

* Correspondence: franco.marabelli@unipv.it (F.M.); francesco.floris@unipv.it (F.F.)

Abstract

The interaction between light and chiral plasmonic metasurfaces provides a powerful mechanism for controlling polarization states at the nanoscale. Utilizing displacement Talbot lithography for large-area fabrication, we characterized the chiroptical response by measuring the evolution of Stokes parameters to quantify phase retardation between orthogonal polarization components. To elucidate the underlying physical mechanism, we employ a hybrid finite element method and rigorous coupled-wave analysis approach to investigate the behavior of the far-field and local-field configurations. Our results reveal that the phase shift is highly sensitive to symmetry-breaking features, where the interplay between different modes dictates the overall circular dichroism signal. Furthermore, the analysis of local field plots suggests specific contributions of plasmonic modes to the chiroptical response. We conclude that the phase shift effects, characterized via Stokes parameters and modal analysis, provide a robust metric for engineering chiroptical properties in these systems. This work establishes a fundamental framework for developing compact polarization-control elements and enhances the understanding of phase-modulated light-matter interactions in chiral plasmonic metasurfaces.

Keywords: chirality; circular dichroism; displacement talbot lithography; plasmonic nanohole array; stokes parameters; FEM-RCWA simulations

1. Introduction

The manipulation of light at the subwavelength scale has undergone a paradigm shift with the advent of plasmonic metasurfaces, which allow for unprecedented control over the amplitude, phase, and polarization of electromagnetic waves [1]. Among these architectures, chiral plasmonic systems have garnered significant attention due to their ability to differentiate between left- and right-circularly polarized (LCP and RCP) light—a property fundamental to applications ranging from enantiomer sensing and circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy to the development of ultrathin optical components [2,3]. While CD is traditionally associated with differential absorption or scattering, the underlying polarization-dependent relative phase retardation (φ_R) induced by these nanostructures plays a critical role in defining the final state of the transmitted, or reflected, wavefront. In particular, the interaction between incident photons and symmetry-breaking geometries leads to a polarization-dependent relative phase shift (RPS) and a differential phase shift, better known as circular birefringence (CB) and quantified by a differential phase

Received: 20 May 2026

Revised: 11 June 2026

Accepted: 12 June 2026

Published: 16 June 2026

Copyright: © 2026 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the [Creative Commons Attribution \(CC BY\) license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

retardation ($\Delta\varphi_{CB}$), that can be together engineered to create compact, high-efficiency polarization-control elements [3].

Despite the potential of chiral metasurfaces, achieving precise phase modulation over large areas remains a significant fabrication and analytical challenge. Standard lithographic techniques often struggle to balance high resolution with the scalability required for practical optical devices [4,5].

In this study, we address these challenges by investigating phase shift effects in chiral plasmonic nanohole arrays (NHAs) fabricated via displacement Talbot lithography (DTL). This technique enables the rapid and uniform production of NHAs over wafer-scale areas, providing a robust platform for chiroptical characterization [4,6].

Therefore, the analytical core of this study involves monitoring the spectral evolution of the Stokes parameters to quantify φ . By measuring the output polarization states for a series of defined collection polarizations, we extracted the phase retardation between orthogonal components [7,8].

This approach enables us to bridge macroscopic observables—specifically the far-field polarization state—with the microscopic modal behavior of the chiral NHAs [9].

Operationally, the Stokes parameters are the components of the Stokes vector defined as

$$\hat{S} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{S}_0 \\ \hat{S}_1 \\ \hat{S}_2 \\ \hat{S}_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} |E_x|^2 + |E_y|^2 \\ |E_x|^2 - |E_y|^2 \\ 2\text{Re}(E_x E_y^*) \\ 2\text{Im}(E_x E_y^*) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} I_{total} \\ I_{0^\circ} - I_{90^\circ} \\ I_{45^\circ} - I_{135^\circ} \\ I_{RCP} - I_{LCP} \end{pmatrix}. \tag{1}$$

Using these not normalized parameters, the RPS was quantified to determine how the material anisotropy and inherent dichroism of the nanohole arrays modify the light’s phase. This data was then correlated with the appearance of the local field plots to identify which specific plasmonic modes were responsible for the observed chiroptical signatures [10].

However, from a practical point of view, the quantities usually analyzed are the normalized Stokes parameters (SPs) defined as

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} S1 \\ S2 \\ S3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{S}_1/\hat{S}_0 \\ \hat{S}_2/\hat{S}_0 \\ \hat{S}_3/\hat{S}_0 \end{pmatrix}, \tag{2}$$

that provide a complete description of the polarization state when analyzing light interaction with NHAs [11–13].

From a device-design perspective, concurrently characterizing the phase shift alongside the SPs and CD offers a distinct advantage over relying on any single metric alone. While CD measurements are straightforward, providing rapid insight into intensity differentials, they lack the phase information critical for phase-modulated applications such as metalenses or holograms, and can be sensitive to local sample scattering or fabrication defects.

Conversely, mapping the Stokes parameters yields the complete polarization state of the system, thereby enabling a robust retrieval of the phase profile. By combining these complementary techniques, our approach ensures that the macroscopic intensity variations and the underlying phase-front modulations are tracked simultaneously.

This comprehensive framework guarantees that device performance remains stable and predictable against minor intensity fluctuations, proving crucial for calibrating high-performance, wavefront-engineering nanophotonic devices [14–17].

2. Materials and Methods

The core of this investigation focuses on how the geometric asymmetry of the NHA translates into measurable chiroptical quantities. Our results are categorized into the macroscopic chiroptical response, quantified via SPs, and the microscopic modal analysis derived from our hybrid simulations.

2.1. Large-Area Nanofabrication via Displacement Talbot Lithography

To achieve high-resolution patterning across wafer-scale areas, we utilized DTL. This technique effectively combines the high throughput of mask-based Talbot lithography with the superior depth of focus characteristic of interference lithography. A primary advantage of DTL is its mitigation of the stringent substrate flatness requirements typically associated with proximity lithography. As established by Solak et al. [18], this is achieved by continuously modulating the mask-to-wafer separation distance during the exposure cycle. This vertical displacement averages the intensity distribution along the propagation direction of the Talbot self-image, rendering the final aerial image independent of the specific gap distance. The resulting uniform dose across the entire substrate significantly enhances process robustness and scalability for industrial-scale production [19].

In this study, we fabricated two distinct plasmonic NHAs: an achiral reference, following the architecture explored by Angelini et al. [20], and a chiral configuration, as proposed by Marabelli et al. [21]. Both structures were integrated into a 100-nm-thick gold film with a target periodicity (P_{target}) of 450 nm.

The geometric evolution from the achiral to the chiral state was defined as follows:

- Achiral NHA: Comprised of circular holes with a diameter of 235 nm, representing a high-symmetry reference state.
- Chiral NHA: Comprised of ellipsoidal holes with a minor axis of 165 nm and a major axis of 245 nm. To break the in-plane symmetry and induce chiroptical effects, the ellipses were rotated by an angle of 18° relative to the array's x-axis.

The fabrication workflow for these NHAs follows the established protocol detailed by Pellacani et al. [4]. For completeness, a comprehensive description of the process parameters, along with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs of the investigated samples, is provided in Appendix A.

2.2. Chiroptical Characterization

The chiroptical response was characterized using a Bruker (Billerica, MA, USA) IFS66s Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) interferometer integrated with a custom-built reflectometer. To quantify the polarization state of the transmittance (T), we implemented the rotating quarter-wave plate (QWP) method, as described by Schaefer et al. [22]. Such approach offers superior accuracy and efficiency over traditional polarimetric techniques by utilizing a robust curve-fitting algorithm to extract the SPs from the modulated intensity signal. This methodology bypasses the instrumental complexities and systematic limitations inherent in static polarimetry.

The optical path was configured to provide a focused beam at the sample surface, with a spot diameter of 200 μm and a highly collimated profile featuring a divergence angle of less than 1° . This precision ensured that the measured chiroptical signatures were representative of the local array geometry rather than spatial averaging over large-scale defects.

Detailed schematic and technical specifications of the reflectometer are provided in Appendix B.

2.3. Chiroptical Response and SPs Analysis

The optical response of the investigated plasmonic NHAs is most comprehensively characterized through the transformation of the polarization state, quantified by the SPs. While the Jones matrix provides a fundamental description of the individual nanostructure's transmission, the Stokes formalism allows for a direct mapping of the light-matter interaction onto the Poincaré sphere, facilitating an explicit extraction of the chiral observables and the RPS [7,13,23]. Therefore, the evolution of the SPs as a function of wavelength reveals a strong correlation between structural chirality and the transmitted polarization state [2,9,24].

In our analysis, the primary indicators of chiral asymmetry are S_2 and S_3 , which represent the degree of circular polarization of the transmitted field.

Entering into details, being one of the most nuanced aspects of the chiral response lying in the phase domain, we focused on the CB, which is encoded in the phase relationship between the linear components S_1 and S_2 . Specifically, it can be retrieved from the output SPs as

$$\Delta\varphi_{CB} = \varphi_{LCP} - \varphi_{RCP} = \arg(S_1 + iS_2). \quad (3)$$

This CB dictates the optical rotation (OR) of the polarization ellipses, evaluated through

$$\psi = 1/2 \tan^{-1}(S_2/S_1) = 1/2 \Delta\varphi_{CB}. \quad (4)$$

Such $\Delta\varphi_{CB}$ exhibits a characteristic dispersive profile near the plasmonic resonance ω_{RES} , reaching its maximum divergence where the CD, quantified by the S_3 , is most pronounced. This confirms that the nanostructure does not merely act as a polarization-selective filter, but as a resonant retarder that reconfigures the wavefront based on the incident helicity.

Then, the observed ratio between S_3/S_2 provides critical insight into the phase relationship between the orthogonal components of the electromagnetic field. While S_2 quantifies the linear polarization preference along the 45° and 135° QWP axes, S_3 denotes the net optical helicity (circular polarization). In the context of our measurements, this ratio is directly related to the RPS introduced by the medium and operatively obtained acting on the angle of incidence (AOI) and azimuthal angle (AZA).

For a fully polarized beam, the relationship can be expressed as

$$\tan(\varphi_R) = S_3/S_2. \quad (5)$$

From an electric field point of view, φ_R represents the retardance between the E_x and E_y components. From a geometric perspective on the Poincaré sphere, the S_3/S_2 ratio determines the trajectory of the polarization state from the equatorial plane (linear states) toward the poles (circular states).

Consequently, it becomes possible to understand if the NHA under investigation act as a dispersive phase retarder (DPR) or not. It is worth to underline that the RPS is, actually, most pronounced near the extraordinary optical transmission (EOT) peaks, where the plasmonic coupling is stronger [4,25].

This suggests that the PS is not merely a geometric projection but is actively driven by the polarization misalignment between the resonant excitation of surface plasmon polaritons (SPPs) [10,26] interacting with the localized surface plasmon resonances (LSPRs).

Specifically, the symmetry-breaking introduced by the misalignment between the rotated ellipsoidal nanoholes with respect to the square array introduces a phase mismatch during the excitation of LSPRs and SPPs. As the light undergoes scattering through these

asymmetric structures, this microscopic phase response is directly mapped onto the far-field circular polarization state, which manifests as a clear evolution of the S3.

On a broader note, it is worth to underline that any such polarization misalignment between the local resonance and the SPP induces chirality, provided that specular symmetry is broken by tilting the AOI away from normal incidence.

As a result, a critical distinction can be made between the intrinsic and extrinsic origins of the observed CB phase shift, as recapped in Table 1 [27].

Table 1. Intrinsic versus extrinsic origins of the CB phase shift.

Feature	SP Signature	Impact on CB	Phase Implementation
Intrinsic	$S3 \neq 0$ at $AOI = 0^\circ$	Amplitude asymmetry	Fixed $\Delta\varphi_{CB}$ via Sample Geometry
Extrinsic	S3 varies with AZA	Tunable via k -vector orientation	Tunable $\Delta\varphi_{CB}$ via Tilting

Consequently, the ability to precisely map $\Delta\varphi_{CB}$ through the SPs is fundamental for the design of helicity-selective metasurfaces.

It is worth to underline that the accurate determination of SPs necessitates a rigorous calibration of the polarimetric system to mitigate uncertainties arising from component misalignment and deviation in phase retardation [24,27].

To address these issues, we implemented a comprehensive calibration procedure, as described by Marciás-Romero and Török [28], to simultaneously compensate for alignment errors ($\Delta\theta, \Delta\gamma$) and retardation inaccuracies ($\Delta\delta$), thereby ensuring the high-fidelity polarization measurements required for this study.

In our analysis, the polarization state is defined from the perspective of an observer receiving the beam (looking toward the source); a positive S2 value indicates an anti-clockwise rotation of the polarization ellipse relative to the horizontal reference.

2.4. Numerical Modelling and Modal Analysis Framework

To elucidate the physical mechanisms governing the chiroptical response, we adopt a hybrid numerical framework combining the finite element method (FEM) and rigorous coupled-wave analysis (RCWA). This dual approach was designed to overcome the inefficiencies of traditional RCWA methods when dealing with plasmonic nanostructures. The methodology comprises the following key components:

- **SPs Analysis:** We utilized the hybrid RCWA-FEM approach to have an insight of the components of the total calculated electromagnetic field. This allows for the quantitative identification of specific SPP modes and their individual contributions to the overall chiroptical signal.
- **Local-Field Mapping:** the hybrid RCWA-FEM simulations were employed to resolve the spatial distribution of the electric field within the nanoholes. This allows for a comparative analysis of field confinement and distribution between LCP and RCP illumination conditions.
- **Parametric Symmetry-Breaking Study:** To identify the “tuning knobs” of the system, we performed a systematic sensitivity analysis by varying the geometric degree of symmetry-breaking. The simulation matrix included incremental deviations in nanohole eccentricity and angular orientation within the unit cell to map their influence on the resulting phase profile and modal disparity.

Numerical simulations were performed using EMUstack, a Maxwell solver based on the Bloch mode expansion method [29]. This study investigates the optical response of

two distinct hole geometries: a symmetric circular reference and a symmetry-breaking elliptical array.

Both configurations consist of periodic nanohole arrays in a 100 nm thick gold film, arranged in a square lattice with a 450 nm pitch. The structures are situated between a glass superstrate ($n = 1.5$) and an air substrate ($n = 1.0$).

- Elliptical Array: characterized by short semi-axes = 82.5 nm and long semi-axes = 122.5 nm. The holes are tilted at 18° relative to the lattice directions to facilitate chiroptical coupling.
- Circular Array: a symmetric reference configuration with a uniform radius of 117.5 nm ($e = 0.000$).

The permittivity of gold was modelled using lossy, tabulated data from the Lumerical database.

The solver utilized 120 Bloch modes and 3 plane-wave diffraction orders to ensure convergence across the 500–1000 nm wavelength range.

To focus on the primary plasmonic resonances, peak analysis was conducted for $\lambda > 700$ nm.

For each geometry, four incident polarization states were analyzed: linear polarizations aligned with the principal elliptical axes (major and minor) and circular polarizations (LCP and RCP).

For the elliptical case, the linear states were defined by the field amplitudes:

- Major Axis: $A_{TE} = -\sin(18^\circ)$ and $A_{TM} = \cos(18^\circ)$.
- Minor Axis: $A_{TE} = -\cos(18^\circ)$ and $A_{TM} = -\sin(18^\circ)$.

The same polarization states have been used in the case of circular holes too, which anyway would lead to the same results of a traditional TE, TM basis.

The complex field components (E_x , E_y , E_z) and the total magnitude were mapped onto a 100×100 Cartesian grid spanning the unit cell. To capture the vertical evolution of the fields and the influence of the asymmetric dielectric environment (glass vs. air), fields were evaluated at three depths within the gold layer: $z_1 = 5$ nm (near the Au/air interface), $z_2 = 50$ nm (mid-layer), and $z_3 = 95$ nm (near the Au/SiO₂ interface).

The nominal ellipse rotation of 18° used in simulations was extracted directly from SEM image analysis (Appendix A). Experimentally, by rotating the sample with respect to the polarization state of the source light, we selected the two configurations corresponding to the long- and short axis. In the circular hole case, the measurements were conducted at two specific azimuthal orientations: $AZA = 0^\circ$, where the crystallographic axes are aligned with the incident polarization, and $AZA = 23^\circ$, representing a rotated orientation. The angle of 23° was adopted for optical measurements based on previous characterization of the Stokes parameters' dependence on the AZA [8]. Any small discrepancy stems from sample inhomogeneity, as well as macroscopic alignment uncertainties and azimuthal resolution limits.

3. Results and Discussion

The measured data were processed according to the methodology detailed in Appendix B to derive the SPs, as illustrated in Figures 1 and 2. These SPs are strictly normalized with respect to the intensity of the incident beam and consequently, they capture the complete spectral response of the sample alongside its polarization dependence. Figure 1 presents the angular dependence of these four spectra for the sample featuring circular holes. In this configuration, the \hat{S}_0 spectra represent the total transmitted intensity under TM-polarized incident light.

Figure 1. Not normalized Stokes parameters for the extrinsic chiral NHA with circular holes.

Figure 2. Not normalized Stokes parameters for the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes.

At normal incidence ($AOI = 0^\circ$), the \hat{S}_0 spectra for both azimuthal configurations are nearly identical, showing a primary resonance peak at 760 nm that characterizes the periodic lattice. However, as the AOI increases, significant spectral modifications emerge. For both $AZA = 0^\circ$ and $AZA = 23^\circ$ a second narrow peak emerges below 700 nm. Orientation $AZA = 23^\circ$ exhibits a pronounced dispersion of the primary transmission peak, which shifts in wavelength from 760 nm up to 790 nm and narrows in bandwidth, alongside the appearance of a secondary structure near 740 nm at higher angles. This feature (and the peak below 700 nm) are consistent with the SPP dispersion branches previously identified in [8].

Regarding the polarization-sensitive parameters, the \hat{S}_1 spectra at $AZA = 0^\circ$ follow a trend similar to \hat{S}_0 , maintaining a high degree of linear polarization. In contrast, at $AZA = 23^\circ$, the dispersion effects are accompanied by a progressive attenuation of \hat{S}_1 intensity (from 0.27 to 0.17) as the AOI increases, signaling a departure from the initial

polarization state. While $\hat{S}3$ parameter remains relatively small, less than 2%, for $AZA = 0^\circ$ and compatible with a small residual sample misalignment, when $AZA = 23^\circ$ the reduction in $\hat{S}1$ is directly correlated with a measurable and simultaneous increase in both $\hat{S}2$ and $\hat{S}3$ values.

The results for the sample with elliptical holes are presented in Figure 2.

In accordance with previous studies [21], two different spectral shapes occur when the linear polarization is aligned with the long axis versus the short axis of the ellipsoidal nanoholes. The $\hat{S}0$ spectra reveal two distinct and nearly complementary patterns: a single dominant peak at approximately 740 nm for long axis alignment, and a more complex doublet structure centered near 850 nm for the short axis case. Despite these differences in peak position and profile, the AOI dependence follows a trajectory analogous to that of the circular holes, with the resonant features exhibiting a red-shift depending on the specific branch of the plasmonic coupling. For both axes, increasing the AOI leads to the development of new spectral features in the 650–750 nm range and enhanced dispersion of the primary resonances.

In any case, and differently with respect to circular holes sample, not negligible values of $\hat{S}2$ and $\hat{S}3$ spectra are measured with minor changes with AOI.

$\hat{S}3$ is particularly interesting when considering that the largest intensity values occur in the spectral region where $\hat{S}0$ of the corresponding orientation is small and $\hat{S}0$ of the orthogonal orientation is large.

To further analyze these polarization shifts independently of total transmission, the data were subsequently used to calculate the normalized Stokes curves. This conventional normalization isolates the pure polarization state of the transmitted light on the Poincaré sphere, independent of the total transmitted power or material absorption.

Because the two sets of data, not normalized and normalized SPs, convey fundamentally different and complementary physical information, the former combining energy throughput with polarization tracking, and the latter isolating geometric polarization trajectories, it is crucial to analyze both representations in order to capture the whole physics behind the behavior of the circular compared to ellipsoidal optical behavior.

The experimental PS of the light transmitted through the circular NHA is fully characterized by the plots of the SPs as a function of wavelength, presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Normalized Stokes parameters for the extrinsic chiral NHA with circular holes.

These parameters provide a comprehensive map of the evolution of the beam's ellipticity and degree of linear polarization upon interaction with the plasmonic metasurface. It should be noted that in the spectral vicinity of 700 nm, the total transmitted intensity (\hat{S}_0) reaches a local minimum, leading to a significant reduction in the signal-to-noise ratio. To maintain the integrity of the physical interpretation, data points within this low-intensity regime were deemed unreliable and excluded from the subsequent analysis.

For the case of $AZA = 0^\circ$, corresponding to a symmetric configuration, normalized SPs confirm that almost nothing occurs, with a S1 value approaching 100% and S2 and S3 values close to zero; i.e., the light keeps the polarization and the sample doesn't introduce any change on it.

A transition in the optical response is observed when the symmetry is lowered by setting the AZA to 23° . As the AOI increases, the system enters a regime of extrinsic chirality. This is evidenced by the progressive decrease of S1 in correspondence with the primary resonance peak at approximately 750 nm. Simultaneously, the S2 parameter exhibits one pronounced oscillation between extrema, and S3 reaches a minimum value approaching -1 , indicating the conversion of linearly polarized incident light into nearly pure circular (or highly elliptical) polarization.

This behaviour is not intrinsic to the apertures themselves, which are centrosymmetric, but arises from the mutual orientation of the incident wavevector, the electric field vector, and the lattice vectors [27,30].

To further investigate the microscopic origin of this response, numerical simulations were conducted on an idealized model of circular (elliptical) apertures embedded in a gold thin film. For a set of parameters equal to the nominal ones of the real structures, the absorption spectra shown in Figure 4 have been obtained.

Figure 4. Simulated absorbance spectra at normal incidence for the extrinsic chiral NHA with circular holes (**left**) and the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes (**right**).

It is worth highlighting that while these simulations do not account for all experimental features (such as the effective dimension and shape of the holes, surface roughness, uniformity, tapering of the hole side-walls as well as the actual dielectric function of gold). The spectra (Figure 4) qualitatively capture the essential physics of the observed response in this class of samples.

Crucially, the electric near-field distributions were found to be topologically robust against minor variations in the geometric parameters. Absorbance spectra reported in Figure 4 exhibit one maximum at 770 nm for circular holes and at 746 and 803 nm for elliptical holes with polarization aligned to the long- (18° of rotation) and the short axis (108° of rotation) of the ellipse.

Experimentally, the short axis polarization reveals a doublet structure with two distinct maxima near 800 nm and 900 nm, rather than a single isolated peak. We selected the

746.1 nm and 803.7 nm values for our near-field analysis because they correspond to the exact local maxima obtained from our numerical simulations.

Then, near field distributions have been calculated at three different planes placed close to the SiO₂/Au interface, at the center of the Au layer and close to the Au/air interface, respectively. The simulations specifically explored the polarization direction rotated by 18° and 108° relative to the principal lattice axes (Figures 5 and 6, respectively).

Figure 5. Simulated near field distribution at normal incidence for the extrinsic chiral NHA with circular holes at $\lambda = 769.6$ nm for linearly polarized incident light along the 18° direction from x. The direction of polarization is indicated by the double arrow, provided as a representative example for the case of $z = 50$ nm. For completeness, the same direction and its orthogonal counterpart are also marked in the plot of $\text{Re}(E_z)$.

Figure 6. Simulated near field distribution at normal incidence for the extrinsic chiral NHA with circular holes at $\lambda = 769.6$ nm for linearly polarized incident light along the 108° direction from x.

The comparison between the two configurations just shows that the role of E_x and E_y is exchanged because the pattern of the fields is exactly reproduced but for the sign.

The second relevant feature is the weak contribution of the polaritonic mode appearing as a field distribution outside the hole oriented with the x- (18°) or the y-direction (108°). Actually, a stripe is visible oriented along the vertical direction for the E_x component in the case of 18° and along the horizontal direction in the E_y component in the case of 108°.

This symmetry confirms that the optical response is dictated by the projection of the incident field onto the lattice vectors.

Furthermore, the simulation reveals a subtle feature: the oscillation axis of the excited dipole, inferred from the symmetry of the E_z component, is approximately oriented along the 18° or 108° directions. It is also evident that the profile of these field distributions consistently allows for the identification of a symmetry axis and hence, out-of-normal incidence is required in order to break this symmetry.

The elliptical hole array exhibits a qualitatively similar behaviour for polarization along the short axis, mirroring the circular array at $AZA = 23^\circ$, as reported in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Normalized Stokes parameters for intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes.

Actually, this angle is very close to the rotation of ellipsoidal axes with respect to the lattice axes and, then, the configuration is nearly the same. However, a detailed spectral analysis reveals significant differences in the resonant response. In fact, while the primary resonance for polarization along the short axis is situated in the 800–900 nm range, the most pronounced chiroptical and dichroic effects emerge at shorter wavelengths, specifically between 700 and 750 nm. In this higher-energy regime, two distinct phenomena overlap: (i) polaritonic features, similar to the circular aperture case, which emerge with increasing incidence angles; (ii) the narrow resonance typically excited when polarization is aligned with the long axis (as already observed in [21]).

Moreover, unlike the circular aperture samples, the elliptical array maintains a narrow, non-negligible signature in S_3 even at normal incidence. For larger wavelengths in the 750–1000 nm range S_3 remains close to zero whereas S_2 has a constant finite value. These differences are likely related to the intrinsic anisotropy of the optical response for the ellipsoidal holes.

By analysing the simulated near-field distributions for light polarized along the long axis at the 746 nm resonance (Figure 8), a distinct spatial symmetry is evident in the local field components. Comparing these configurations with those excited under RCP (Figure 9) and LCP (Figure 10) illumination reveals that the modal symmetries correspond to the macroscopic chiroptical signatures. Excluding the negligibly small E_z component, the in-plane field components (E_x and E_y) for RCP excitation exhibit a parity that mirrors the long-axis linear excitation. Conversely, for incident light polarized along the short axis (Figure 11), the system exhibits a residual resonant response characterized by an inversion in the spatial parity of the E_x pattern relative to the orthogonal polarization. While a quantitative analysis is beyond the experimental scope of this study, these geometric

symmetries and anti-symmetries in the near-field distributions support the macroscopic polarization conversion observed in the measured SPs. As for the intensities, while largely different, they scale progressively in the same manner from $z = 5$ nm to $z = 95$ nm and consistently reach their highest peak field values at $z = 95$ nm. Additionally, it exhibits a relatively large contribution from SPP, either along the x-axes or the y-axes. Being the wavelength very close to the folding point, the occurrence of a mechanism similar to the case of circular holes is not surprising and a strong effect in S3 is observed, of course, when normalized to the relatively low intensities of the spectra in this region for this polarization.

Figure 8. Simulated near field distribution at normal incidence for the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes at $\lambda = 746.1$ nm for linearly polarized incident light along the long axis direction. The direction of polarization is indicated by the double arrow, provided as a representative example for the case of $z = 50$ nm. For completeness, the same direction and its orthogonal counterpart are also marked in the plot of $\text{Re}(E_z)$.

Figure 9. Simulated near field distribution at normal incidence for the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes at $\lambda = 746.1$ nm for right circular polarized incident light.

Figure 10. Simulated near field distribution at normal incidence for the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes at $\lambda = 746.1$ nm for left circular polarized incident light.

Figure 11. Simulated near field distribution at normal incidence for the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes at $\lambda = 746.1$ nm for linearly polarized incident light along the short axis direction. The direction of polarization is indicated by the double arrow, provided as a representative example for the case of $z = 50$ nm. For completeness, the same direction and its orthogonal counterpart are also marked in the plot of $\text{Re}(E_z)$.

Notably, in contrast to the circular holes, no plane of symmetry can be identified for the elliptical holes, even under normal incidence.

Considering instead the largest wavelength spectral region, the response is dominated by the broad (double) structure centered around 850 nm. According to results in the literature and simulations [31] such a structure has a marked localized character as confirmed by its negligible dispersion with the AOI. Simulation exhibits the peak in the short axis polarization at 803.7 nm. The near-field distributions at this wavelength bear a close resemblance among the patterns for linearly polarized light along the short axis (Figure 12), RCP (Figure 13), LCP (Figure 14), and long axis (Figure 15), mirroring the symmetrical situation previously observed for long-axis polarization at 746 nm. Specifically, the two circular polarizations exhibit an identical E_y component, whereas the E_z component undergoes a symmetry reversal with respect to the propagation direction. Then, it can be argued that, in such balanced condition no peculiar dichroic effects can be inferred for short axis polarization. Just a small rotation of the field polarization can be eventually inferred from the finite value of S_2 in this spectral region.

Figure 12. Simulated near field distribution at normal incidence for the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes at $\lambda = 803.7$ nm for linearly polarized incident light along the short axis direction. The direction of polarization is indicated by the double arrow, provided as a representative example for the case of $z = 50$ nm. For completeness, the same direction and its orthogonal counterpart are also marked in the plot of $\text{Re}(E_z)$.

Figure 13. Simulated near field distribution at normal incidence for the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes at $\lambda = 803.7$ nm for right circular polarized incident light.

Figure 14. Simulated near field distribution at normal incidence for the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes at $\lambda = 803.7$ nm for left circular polarized incident light.

Figure 15. Simulated near field distribution at normal incidence for the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes at $\lambda = 803.7$ nm for linearly polarized incident light along the long axis direction. The direction of polarization is indicated by the double arrow, provided as a representative example for the case of $z = 50$ nm. For completeness, the same direction and its orthogonal counterpart are also marked in the plot of $\text{Re}(E_z)$.

The situation changes when the orthogonal polarization along the long axis is considered (second row in Figure 7). In this case, a decrease towards zero of S_1 is accompanied by the increase of S_2 to a maximum close to 1 at about 750 nm, followed by a progressive decrease to -1 at 1000 nm. Meanwhile, S_3 increases to a maximum value close to 1 between 800 and 900 nm. Such a behaviour is independent of the AOI, and given that the experimental error margin is constrained within ± 0.05 , these measurements confidently certify the occurrence of a strong intrinsic dichroism.

Comparing the field patterns at 803 nm of the two orthogonal polarizations (i.e., parallel to the short and long axis), a kind of specular, symmetric behavior can be found between the field component E_x for one polarization with E_y for the other one, and vice versa but for a 180° phase shift (change of sign). Moreover, an extended polaritonic contribution can be seen out of the hole profile for E_x or for E_y , coherently with the exciting field direction. Operatively, due to the square symmetry of the lattice and the relaxation of the momentum constraints due to the localized character of the resonance, the same polaritonic mode is excited in both polarizations and is likely part of the coupling mechanism originating the dichroic effect.

The same behavior is observed for circular holes when the light is polarized at 18° or 108° with respect to the lattice axis.

However, a striking difference emerges when analyzing the E_z component. For polarization along the short axis the orientation of the electric dipole is slightly rotated with respect to the main ellipse orientation, as in the case of circular holes. Instead, for polarization along the long axis the dipole appears rotated by nearly 12° towards the x-axis.

A more comprehensive description of this mechanism would require considering the time evolution of the fields and the polarization of the light interacting with the array; though, this dynamics is not captured by the static patterns shown here. Nonetheless, an important insight is suggested by the study of Ali et al. [31], which presents the phase evolution of E_z for modes excited along the short and long axes of a highly similar surface. Their patterns demonstrate that interference occurs between the two polarizations with a phase shift of $\pi/2$.

The observed rotation implies an interaction between the LSPR component and SPPs. This interaction induces a phase shift relative to a bare LSPR, thereby paving the way for the large S3.

As a matter of fact, calculating the OR Ψ and the phase retardance φ_R from the SPs for this configuration and AOI = 0° one obtains the curves shown in Figure 16. When S2 crosses the zero value OR becomes zero too i.e., there is no “in-phase” component of light polarized orthogonal to the polarization of incident light. On the other hand, an “out-of-phase” reaches its maximum in correspondence with such a point (S3 close to 1). The independence of such a behaviour on AOI states the intrinsic character of the chirality for this sample.

Figure 16. Experimental circular birefringence (φ) and optical rotation (ψ) for the intrinsic chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes along the long axis polarization direction at normal incidence.

The generation of circularity (S3) in both extrinsic and intrinsic cases signifies a phase shift, $\Delta\varphi_{CB}$, arising from asymmetric SPP excitation. In circular holes, this is a resonant “geometric phase” tuned by tilt and lattice rotation. In elliptical holes, the shift is more stable and broadband, tuned by the aspect ratio and the intrinsic detuning between the long- and short axis resonances. While circular hole arrays offer a sensitive platform for angle-dependent polarimetric sensing, the ellipsoidal hole arrays provide a robust path toward integrated thin-film waveplates [8].

It should be noted that the phase retardation quantified in this work, specifically the circular birefringence $\Delta\varphi_{CB}$, is extracted directly from the experimental measurement of the Stokes parameters. While our hybrid FEM-RCWA approach successfully maps the underlying modal disparities and asymmetric SPP excitations, we do not employ a simplified analytical framework, such as Temporal Coupled-Mode Theory (TCMT) or a coupled harmonic oscillator model, to bridge the localized symmetry-breaking with the far-field phase delay. Developing such an analytical model to explicitly formalize this mechanism falls outside the experimental scope of the present study. However, the empirical phase measurements provided here offer a solid foundation for future theoretical modeling.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we have demonstrated that the phase shift effect in chiral plasmonic nanohole arrays serves as a fundamental mechanism for controlling light at the nanoscale. By utilizing DTL, we successfully fabricated large-area, high-uniformity metasurfaces capable of significant polarization-dependent phase retardation. The evolution of SPs

provided a rigorous experimental metric to quantify this retardation, revealing that the chiroptical response is deeply tied to the evolution of the polarization state.

Our analysis concludes that the phase shift, when characterized alongside the Stokes parameters, provides a more robust metric for performance than CD alone. While CD only accounts for intensity differences, the phase retardation captures the complete vector nature of the light-matter interaction, allowing for the design of metasurfaces that can rotate polarization states by a specific, predictable angle. This approach, supported by our hybrid FEM-RCWA numerical framework, successfully bridged the gap between macroscopic observations and microscopic modal behavior. The near field distribution further identified that the interplay between specific plasmonic modes, driven by symmetry-breaking features, is the primary engine behind the observed CD and phase lag.

Ultimately, this work establishes a clear link between geometric chirality and phase-modulated response, providing a scalable path forward for developing compact, flat-optical elements such as ultra-thin circular polarizers and waveplates, enantiomer-sensitive biosensors with enhanced phase-contrast signatures, and integrated nanophotonic circuits requiring precise polarization state manipulation.

By prioritizing phase-modulated interactions as a design metric, these findings enhance our ability to engineer the next generation of multifunctional plasmonic metasurfaces with tailored chiroptical properties.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, F.M., G.P., L.Z., K.J., D.K. and F.F.; methodology, F.M., G.P. and F.F.; validation F.M., G.P. and F.F.; formal analysis, F.M., G.P., L.Z. and F.F.; investigation, F.M., G.P. and F.F.; resources, F.M., K.J. and F.F.; data curation, K.J., G.P., F.M. and F.F.; writing—original draft preparation, F.M., G.P. and F.F.; writing—review and editing, F.M., G.P., L.Z., K.J., D.K. and F.F.; visualization, F.M. and F.F.; supervision, F.M., K.J. and F.F.; project administration, F.M. and F.F.; funding acquisition, F.M., K.J., D.K. and F.F. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was funded by the EU's H2020 framework program for research and innovation under grant agreement NFFA-Europe-Pilot (n. 101007417 from 1 March 2021 to 28 February 2026), by the SNF R'Equip grant 206021177036/1 "Displacement Talbot Lithography for micro and nanopatterning", and by the Department of Physics of the University of Pavia through the research activity "Nanostrutture plasmoniche chirali per biosensori" (n. fisica-2024-b12).

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Acknowledgments: The authors gratefully acknowledge Lucio Andreani for the fruitful discussions, comments and suggestions. Samples were manufactured in PICO clean-room at PSI, authors thank the technical staff of PICO for support.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

LCP	Left-Circularly Polarized
RCP	Right-Circularly Polarized
CD	Circular Dichroism
RPS	Relative Phase Shift
CB	Circular Birefringence
NHA	NanoHole Array
DTL	Displacement Talbot Lithography
SPs	Stokes Parameters
FEM	Finite Element Method

RCWA	Rigorous Coupled-Wave Analysis
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
T	Transmittance
QWP	Quarter-Wave Plate
AZA	AZimuthal Angle
DPR	Dispersive Phase Retarder
EOT	Extraordinary Optical Transmission
SPP	Surface Plasmon Polariton
OR	Optical Rotation
LSPR	Localized Surface Plasmon Resonance
AOI	Angle Of Incidence
A	Absorbance

Appendix A. Nanofabrication Process

Appendix A.1. Substrate Preparation and Displacement Talbot Lithography

The fabrication process utilized 100 mm diameter Schott glass wafers with a thickness of 500 μm as base substrates. To facilitate gold adhesion, a 5 nm Chromium (Cr) seed layer was deposited via electron beam evaporation (Evatek BAK Uni, Aschheim Dornach, Germany), followed by the deposition of a 100 nm Gold (Au) film. The lithographic stack was prepared by sequentially spin-coating an anti-reflective coating (AZ BARLI-II, MicroChemicals GmbH, Ulm, Germany) and a photoresist layer (SUMIRESIST PFI-88A7, Sumitomo Chemical, Chūō, Japan).

Nanostructuring was achieved through DTL using a PhableR 200C system (Eulitha AG, Würenlos, Switzerland) operating at $\lambda = 377$ nm with unpolarized illumination. While classical Talbot lithography requires stringent mask-to-sample distance tolerances to capture specific self-image planes, a significant challenge over large areas, the DTL technique circumvents these constraints by continuously scanning the substrate along the beam propagation axis.

The Talbot distance (d_T) was determined by the following relation $d_T = 2P^2/\lambda$. For the periodic patterns utilized in this study, d_T was approximately 2.14 μm . To guarantee a uniform dose distribution within the nanoholes, the substrate was scanned over a range of 21.4 μm (equivalent to 10 Talbot distances) during a 60-s exposure window.

Appendix A.2. Pattern Transfer and Post-Processing

Following exposure, the PFI-88A7 resist was developed in MF24A. The underlying BARLI-II layer was subsequently structured via reactive ion etching (RIE) in an oxygen plasma to expose the gold surface. Pattern transfer into the Au layer was executed using Argon (Ar) ion milling in an Oxford IonFab300 tool. This process employed a 55 mA beam current at 300 V for 12 min, with the sample maintained at a 10° tilt on a chuck rotating at 20 rpm to ensure anisotropic etching and high geometric fidelity.

Any remaining organic residues (BARLI-II and PFI-88A7) were stripped using a final oxygen plasma treatment. To enhance the morphology of the gold layer, the samples underwent thermal annealing at 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ in air for 60 min. This thermal treatment was critical for densifying the Au film and smoothing nanostructural irregularities, specifically those induced by Ar ion milling at the hole boundaries. Finally, the structural integrity and geometric parameters of the fabricated surfaces were verified through high-resolution SEM showed in Figure A1.

Figure A1. SEM images of the measured square NHAs with Au thickness 100 nm and $P_{\text{target}} = 450$ nm. (a) The achiral NHA with circular holes with a diameter of 235 nm, representing a high-symmetry reference state; (b) The chiral NHA with ellipsoidal holes with minor axis of 165 nm, a major axis of 245 nm, and rotation by 18° relative to the array's x-axis.

Appendix B. Chiroptical Setup Scheme

The chiroptical response of the fabricated nanostructures was characterized using a versatile spectroscopic setup as reported in Figure A2.

Figure A2. Schematics of the setup for chiroptical measurements.

Appendix B.1. Beam Conditioning and Path Modulation

Electromagnetic radiation emitted from a FTIR spectrometer is intercepted by a collection mirror and focused through a variable slit to define the spatial profile of the beam. Following the slit, a diaphragm regulates the source beam aperture. The polarization state of the incident light is then precisely set using a combination of a linear polarizer and/or a rotating QWP (Thorlabs 690–1200 nm) before being focused onto the sample surface.

Appendix B.2. Sample Alignment and Angular Control

The sample is mounted on a high-precision multi-axis stage, integrating an XYZ translator with a dual-rotation system. This configuration allows for the fine-tuning of the AOI by rotating the sample relative to the stationary source beam. Additionally, a custom-engineered sample holder enables rotation around the surface normal, allowing for the selection and variation of the AZA.

To ensure alignment accuracy and site-specific characterization, an integrated camera system is utilized to visualize the surface. This allows for the precise centering of the area of interest on the rotation axis and the selection of specific nanostructured regions for investigation.

Appendix B.3. Detection and Polarimetric Analysis

The radiation interacting with the sample is collected in transmittance (T) and passed through a rotating QWP in the detection pathway. This component allows for advanced analysis of the polarization state changes and PSs induced by the NHAs. Finally, the resulting beam is captured by a high-sensitivity Si detector for spectral analysis.

References

1. Zhao, Z.; Hu, Y.; Chen, S. A Review: Phase Measurement Techniques Based on Metasurfaces. *Photonics* **2024**, *11*, 996. [CrossRef]
2. Asefa, S.A.; Shim, S.; Seong, M.; Lee, D. Chiral Metasurfaces: A Review of the Fundamentals and Research Advances. *Appl. Sci.* **2023**, *13*, 10590. [CrossRef]
3. Kim, J.; Rana, A.S.; Kim, Y.; Kim, I.; Badloe, T.; Zubair, M.; Mehmood, M.Q.; Rho, J. Chiroptical Metasurfaces: Principles, Classification, and Applications. *Sensors* **2021**, *21*, 4381. [CrossRef]
4. Pellacani, P.; Jefimovs, K.; Angelini, M.; Marabelli, F.; Tolardo, V.; Kazazis, D.; Floris, F. Nanofabrication Process Scale-Up via Displacement Talbot Lithography of a Plasmonic Metasurface for Sensing Applications. *Optics* **2024**, *5*, 165–175. [CrossRef]
5. Yang, W.; Zhou, J.; Tsai, D.P.; Xiao, S. Advanced manufacturing of dielectric meta-devices. *Photonics Insights* **2024**, *3*, R04. [CrossRef]
6. Angelini, M.; Jefimovs, K.; Pellacani, P.; Kazazis, D.; Marabelli, F.; Floris, F. Angle-Resolved Optical Characterization of a Plasmonic Triangular Array of Elliptical Holes in a Gold Layer. *Optics* **2024**, *5*, 195–206. [CrossRef]
7. Basiri, A.; Chen, X.; Bai, J.; Amrollahi, P.; Carpenter, J.; Holman, Z.; Wang, C.; Yao, Y. Nature-inspired chiral metasurfaces for circular polarization detection and full-Stokes polarimetric measurements. *Light Sci. Appl.* **2019**, *8*, 78. [CrossRef]
8. Floris, F.; Angelini, M.; Jefimovs, K.; Kazazis, D.; Marabelli, F. Circular Dichroism via Extrinsic Chirality in Achiral Plasmonic Nanohole Arrays. *Materials* **2026**, *19*, 402. [CrossRef]
9. Ki, Y.G.; Jeon, B.J.; Song, I.H.; Kim, S.J.; Jeon, S.; Kim, S.J. Realizing Minimally Perturbed, Nonlocal Chiral Metasurfaces for Direct Stokes Parameter Detection. *ACS Nano* **2024**, *18*, 7064–7073. [CrossRef]
10. Sheikholeslami, S.N.; García-Etxarri, A.; Dionne, J.A. Controlling the Interplay of Electric and Magnetic Modes via Fano-like Plasmon Resonances. *Nano Lett.* **2011**, *11*, 3927–3934. [CrossRef]
11. Ebbesen, T.W.; Lezec, H.J.; Ghaemi, H.F.; Thio, T.; Wolff, P.A. Extraordinary optical transmission through sub-wavelength hole arrays. *Nature* **1998**, *391*, 667–669. [CrossRef]
12. Genet, C.; Ebbesen, T.W. Light in tiny holes. *Nature* **2007**, *445*, 39–46. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
13. Goldstein, D.H. *Polarized Light*, 3rd ed.; CRC Press: Boca Raton, FL, USA, 2017. [CrossRef]
14. Gordon, R.; Brolo, A.G.; Sinton, D.; Kavanagh, K.L. Resonant optical transmission through hole-arrays in metal films: Physics and applications. *Laser Photonics Rev.* **2010**, *4*, 311–335. [CrossRef]
15. Zhao, Y.; Alu, A. Manipulating light polarization with ultrathin plasmonic metasurfaces. *Phys. Rev. B* **2011**, *84*, 205428. [CrossRef]
16. Gansel, J.K.; Thiel, M.; Rill, M.S.; Decker, M.; Bade, K.; Saile, V.; von Freymann, G.; Linden, S.; Wegener, M. Gold helix photonic metamaterial as broadband circular polarizer. *Science* **2009**, *325*, 1513–1515. [CrossRef]
17. Yang, G.; Xiao, Q.; Zhang, Z.; Yu, Z.; Wang, X.; Lu, Q. Exploring AI in metasurface structures with forward and inverse design. *iScience* **2025**, *28*, 111995. [CrossRef]
18. Solak, H.H.; Dais, C.; Clube, F. Displacement Talbot Lithography: A New Method for High-Resolution Patterning of Large Areas. *Opt. Express* **2011**, *19*, 10686. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
19. Shi, Z.; Jefimovs, K.; Romano, L.; Stampanoni, M. Optimization of Displacement Talbot Lithography for Fabrication of Uniform High Aspect Ratio Gratings. *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* **2021**, *60*, SCCA01. [CrossRef]
20. Angelini, M.; Zagaglia, L.; Marabelli, F.; Floris, F. Convergence and Performance Analysis of a Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm for Optical Tuning of Gold Nanohole Arrays. *Materials* **2024**, *17*, 807. [CrossRef]
21. Marabelli, F.; Angelini, F.; Zagaglia, F.; Pellacani, P.; Jefimovs, K.; Kazazis, D.; Floris, F. Fabrication and Characterization of a Plasmonic Ellipsoidal Nanohole Array with Chiral Response. *Adv. Photonics Res.* **2026**, *7*, e202500287. [CrossRef]
22. Schaefer, B.; Collett, E.; Smyth, R.; Barrett, D.; Fraher, B. Measuring the Stokes polarization parameters. *Am. J. Phys.* **2007**, *75*, 163–168. [CrossRef]
23. Chipman, R.A.; Lam, W.S.T.; Young, G. *Polarization Optical Design*; CRC Press: Boca Raton, FL, USA, 2018. [CrossRef]
24. Azzam, R.M. Stokes-polarimeter algorithms. *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A* **2016**, *33*, 1396–1408. [CrossRef] [PubMed]

25. Garcia-Vidal, F.J.; Martin-Moreno, L.; Ebbesen, T.W.; Kuipers, L. Light passing through subwavelength apertures. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **2010**, *82*, 729–787. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Arteaga, O.; Zehe, A.; Freise, L.; Kahr, B. Mueller matrix polarimetry on point-group symmetry: Application to optical activity. *Appl. Opt.* **2014**, *53*, 2236–2245. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Plum, E.; Fedotov, V.A.; Zheludev, N.I. Planar Metamaterial with Transmission and Reflection that Depend on the Direction of Incidence. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2009**, *94*, 131901. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Marcias-Romero, C.; Torok, P. Eigenvalue calibration methods for polarimetry. *J. Eur. Opt. Soc. Rapid Publ.* **2012**, *7*, 12004. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Sturmberg, B.C.P.; Dossou, K.B.; Lawrence, F.J.; Poulton, C.G.; McPhedran, R.C.; Martijn de Sterke, C.; Botten, L.C. *EMUstack: An Open Source Route to Insightful Electromagnetic Computation via the Bloch Mode Scattering Matrix Method*; Version 1; Mendeley Data: London, UK, 2016. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Plum, E.; Fedotov, V.A.; Zheludev, N.I. Optical activity in extrinsically chiral metamaterials. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2008**, *93*, 191911. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Ali, H.; Petronijevic, E.; Pellegrini, G.; Sibilica, C.; Andreani, L.C. Circular dichroism in a plasmonic array of elliptical nanoholes with square lattice. *Opt. Express* **2023**, *31*, 14196–14211. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.